

Measuring library consortia performance

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1. Introduction

A framework that enables the evaluation of library consortia –academic, public, or mixed- is useful in the ever-antagonizing world of limited library resources. Publicized evaluation reports could assist libraries to choose when multiple consortia are claiming their attention; or could contribute to the self-assessment for a consortium: if one is seeking to be better, one has to know their strengths and weaknesses. Finally, when deciding to form a new consortium, instead of assuming there is strength in unison, we should be able to calculate what to expect.

There have been former contributions in evaluating consortia or consortia services: using tools like *LibQUAL+* (Gatten, 2004; Lee, 2004; Garthwait and Richardson, 2008) and *MINES for Libraries* (Plum *et al.*, 2010); assessing services, mostly digital material services, either as value-for-money (e.g. ROI or other economic value) or as the quality of service (Melo and Pires, 2012); estimating the economic value of public libraries (Holt and Elliott, 2003; Aabø, 2005; Barron *et al.*, 2005; Ko *et al.*, 2012).

Applying an ISO standard has decisive benefits: easy to apply, world-recognized, an established methodology to make comparisons, a well-known tool that came out of global research. Certain international standards involving library assessment have been produced, such as ISO 16439:2014 “Methods and procedures for assessing the impact of libraries”. The standard, which received a lot of attention from the research community (Poll, 2012; de Jager, 2017; Creaser, 2018), touches upon the methodology and the concepts involved in assessing the impact of libraries. However, it is the ISO11620:2014 “Library performance indicators” that defines specific instruments, namely indicators, to assess the quality of library services. ISO11620 has already been used to measure the performance in individual academic libraries (Ellis *et al.*, 2009; Passonneau, 2013) and public libraries (Eid and Jirjees, 2015).

This paper engages with the question whether we could implement the ISO11620 for collective assessment purposes, meaning to assess a consortium or its services. Do we need new performance indicators or can we adjust some of those already existent in the ISO11620 standard? Moreover, to the best of our knowledge there is no literature published on defining Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for library consortia. Therefore, this paper attempts to investigate whether a subset of the ISO11620 p.i. could be considered KPIs.

2. The proposed approach

The aims as well as the process for the assessment of a consortium’s performance should be very clear to obtain meaningful and useful findings. In general, there are three approaches to ponder on the evaluation of a consortium:

1. Measure the added value of a consortium over what a single library can offer on its own: for instance, an individual library offers its users a number of subscriptions to databases but by participating in a consortium gains access to more subscriptions; the difference in the numbers of subscriptions denotes the added value of the participation to the consortium.
2. Measure the total value of a single library that participates in a consortium: an individual library offers its users a number of subscriptions to databases, while by participating in a consortium gains access to more subscriptions; the sum of the two numbers of subscriptions denotes the total value of the library.

3. Measure the total value of all the libraries that participate in a consortium. For instance, an individual library offers its users a number of X subscriptions to databases; a second individual library offers its users Y subscriptions to databases, while the consortium offers access to Z subscriptions; the sum of all the numbers denotes the total value of all participating libraries.

2.1 Our approach

The investigation of the suitability of ISO11620 performance indicators (p.i.) to measure a consortium's performance is described by the following stages: first, determine which services consortia are most likely to offer to their member libraries. We looked into the bibliography and recorded the services mentioned in broader categories. Then, examine whether ISO11620 provides the appropriate indicators to measure the performance of these services. Consecutively, establish what changes -if any- are needed in the definition, or the data collection methodology for the p.i. to be implemented for collective assessment. The bibliographic sources listed by the standard in each indicator were also consulted. Finally, deepen into the concept and practice of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs); we examined whether the ISO11620 p.i. could be applied as KPIs for the assessment of library consortia.

2.2 Consortia services: a concise overview

A 2006 ALA research found that "the most common services and activities of Library Networks, Cooperatives, and Consortia include 5 services: Communication with member libraries, Resource sharing, General professional development, General consulting and technical assistance, and Cooperative purchasing or group discounts" (Davis, 2009). A more recent study of 65 consortia reported a broader spectrum of services offered to their library members (Horton and Provenitz, 2015, fig. 2.1):

1. Training
2. Shared electronic content
3. Group purchasing
4. Physical delivery
5. Consulting
6. Shared integrated library system (ILS)
7. Mediated interlibrary loan for returnable items
8. Cooperative collection development among members
9. Shared digital repository
10. Mediated document delivery of non-returnable items
11. Cooperative digitization services
12. Summer reading program
13. Cooperative off-site depository (physical)
14. Shared institutional repository

Horton and Provenitz (2015, ch. 4) summarized the consortia activities and services under the headings: "Cataloging, Consulting, Continuing Education and Training, Cooperative Collection Development, Cooperative Purchasing, Digitization Services, Institutional Repositories and the Library as Publisher, Integrated Library Systems, Physical Delivery, Resource Sharing, and Consortia Support Agencies".

An OCLC's research in 2012 listed ILL/Resource Sharing/Document Delivery as the most-used service, followed by Shared Online Catalog (group catalog)/Union List, and Cooperative Purchasing. Electronic Content Licensing, Training,

Technology Management Services, and Personal and Leadership Development are the rest of the commonly used services the report cited (OCLC, 2012).

Besides the above-mentioned researches, Machovec referred to “Group purchasing of electronic resources, Shared integrated library systems, Shared discovery and delivery systems, Shared digital repositories services and hosting, Shared print archiving” as the “most common programmatic areas with consortia” (Machovec, 2013).

In other countries we found similar services to be the consortia’s major offer. For example, “most library consortia in China have focused on sharing resources in the areas of cooperative acquisitions and cataloging, reciprocal borrowing services, interlibrary borrowing and online document delivery, centralized staff training, and technological development” (Dong and Zou, 2009).

2.3 Key Performance Indicators for libraries and consortia

With the concept of KPIs widely used, we needed to define what they are and what they offer in assessing performance. As SCONUL clarified, “Key Performance Indicators are financial and non-financial metrics used to quantify objectives to reflect strategic performance of an organization” (SCONUL, 2021).

According to Parmenter (2020, p. 51), KPIs should be developed from the organisation’s critical success factors. Appleton (2017, Ch. 9) also referred to their ties with the organisation’s strategy: “...the organizational or the library strategy and KPIs need to be closely linked to the outcomes that have been identified through the library's strategic planning”. Unlike usage statistics or input-based metrics, “outcome-derived KPIs can be channeled more easily into concrete, actionable insights, resulting in real changes in systems, processes, and services” (Dalton, 2012).

When an organisation defines their KPIs, they often are aligned with key areas, for example those specified in the Balanced Scorecard approach. Appleton (2017, Ch. 9) referred to specific key measurement areas in relation to libraries: “Customer satisfaction, Financial performance, Internal processes, and Employee development and satisfaction”.

We compared the Appleton’s list of KPIs for libraries (Appleton, 2017, Ch. 12) with the ISO11620 p.i.. The indicators in ISO11620 that have the same scope with the indicators in Appleton’s list are candidate to be KPIs. If an indicator can function as KPI for assessing the performance of a library service, then we assume that this indicator could be also a KPI for a consortium.

3. Findings

3.1 Categorisation of consortia services and the ISO11620

We recorded the services mentioned in the bibliography into the following categories:

1. **Collaborative Collection Development** includes:
 - a. Cooperative purchasing (suggested in Davis, 2009; Dong and Zou, 2009; Horton and Provenitz, 2015; OCLC, 2012)
 - b. Electronic content licensing (mentioned in OCLC, 2012).
 - c. Shared print storage (cited by Horton and Provenitz, 2015; Machovec, 2013).
2. Cooperative **Digitization Services** (referred by Horton and Provenitz, 2015) applies to consortia that host digitization initiatives.
3. **Institutional Repositories** (pointed out by Horton and Provenitz, 2015; Machovec, 2013) is mainly a concern of academic libraries consortia and could refer to both software and hardware infrastructure for collecting scholarly content generated by faculty, staff, and students in an institution.

4. **Programs for Users.** A great number of libraries offer programs or training sessions to their patrons. Several consortia organise summer reading campaigns (*see* Horton and Provenitz, 2015), seniors' technology education or STEM programs and exhibitions.
5. **Resource Sharing and InterLibrary Loan** refers both to physical delivery of borrowed documents and digital resource sharing. Using different terms, the service is mentioned by Davis, 2009; Dong and Zou, 2009; Horton and Provenitz, 2015; OCLC, 2012.
6. **Shared Integrated Library System and Collaborative Cataloguing** comprises common cataloguing practices and a shared catalogue. This service is listed as cooperative cataloging by Dong and Zou, 2009; as shared integrated library system (ILS) by Horton and Provenitz, 2015 and by Machovec, 2013; as shared online catalog (group catalog)/union list by OCLC, 2012.
7. **Staff Training and Consulting** incorporates consulting, continuing education, and training for library personnel, as referred by Davis, 2009; Dong and Zou, 2009; Horton and Provenitz, 2015; OCLC, 2012.
8. **Consortium Management** comprises:
 - a. Technology management services (Dong and Zou, 2009; OCLC, 2012).
 - b. Consortia support (Horton and Provenitz, 2015) services.

3.2 ISO11620 performance indicators and consortia's performance assessment

The ISO11620:2014 "Library performance indicators" is in its 3rd edition. It presents 52 p.i. and organises them according to four major areas of measurement, following the Balanced Scorecard approach:

1. Resources, Access, and Infrastructure
2. Use
3. Efficiency
4. Potentials and Development

For each p.i. we suggest whether it can be used to measure the performance for a consortium service (as cited in chapter 3.1). Table 1 exhibits the assignment of the p.i. to the categories of consortia services. Thus, 10 p.i. are suggested for the *Collaborative Collection Development* category of services (see 3.1.1); 7 p.i. could be used for the category of *Consortium Management* services (see 3.1.8); 4 for *Shared Integrated Library System and Collaborative Cataloguing* (3.1.6) and 3 p.i. for *Resource Sharing and Interlibrary Loan* (3.1.5); 2 indicators could be utilized for each of the following services: *Staff Training* (3.1.7), *User Programs* (3.1.4) and *Digitization* (3.1.2); finally, 1 p.i. could be applied for measuring the performance of *Institutional Repositories* (3.1.3).

The standard also includes additional indicators for services that are not mentioned in the categorization resulted by the bibliography overview. These indicators correspond to significant consortia services: the standard demonstrates 3 indicators for *Reference Services*, which could interest consortia that offer Collaborative Virtual Reference Services, and 2 p.i. for *Material Preservation*, a service concerning consortia with Collaborative Preservation Projects; last but not least, 9 p.i. could contribute to assess the *Needs of the Audience and the General Impact of the Consortium*.

Table 1: Consortia services correlated with the appropriate indicators

Consortia Services	ISO11620 performance indicators*
<i>Collaborative Collection Development</i>	
· Cooperative Purchasing	B.3.1.1 Cost per Collection Use
	B.3.1.2 Acquisition Cost per Collection Use
	B.3.2.1 Median Time of Document Acquisition
	B.3.3.3 Ratio of Acquisition Expenditures to Staff Costs
· Shared Off-site Storage Facilities	B.1.2.1 Shelving Accuracy
	B.1.2.2 Median Time of Document Retrieval from Closed Stacks
	B.1.3.4 Percentage of Storage Space which has an Appropriate Environment
· E-resources	B.1.1.3 Percentage of Rejected Accesses
· E-resources Cooperative Purchasing	B.3.1.3 Cost per Download
	B.4.1.1 Percentage of Expenditure on Information Provision Spent on the Electronic Collection
<i>Consortium Management</i>	
· Consortium Efficiency	B.3.4.1 Cost per User
· Consortium Funding	B.4.3.1 Percentage of Library Means Received by Special Grant or Income Generated
	B.4.3.2 Percentage of Institutional Means Allocated to the Library
· Consortium Human Resources	B.1.4.1 Staff per Capita
	B.3.3.1 User Services Staff as a Percentage of Total Staff
	B.4.2.4 Percentage of Staff in Cooperative Partnerships and Projects
· Technology Management Services	B.4.2.1 Percentage of Library Staff Providing Electronic Services
	B.1.1.4 Number of Documents Digitized per 1.000 Documents in the Collection
	B.2.1.5 Number of Downloads per Document Digitized
	B.1.2.3 Speed of Interlibrary Lending
<i>Resource Sharing & ILL</i> (for physical & electronic collections)	B.1.2.4 Percentage of Successful Interlibrary Loans
	B.3.3.5 Employee Productivity in Lending and Delivery Services
<i>Institutional Repositories</i>	B.1.1.5 Percentage of the Owner Institution's Publications in the Institutional Repository
<i>Material Preservation</i> (Collaborative Preservation Projects)	B.1.2.7 Percentage of the Rare Collection in Stable Condition
	B.1.2.8 Percentage of Rare Materials Needing Conservation/Restoration Treatment that Received Such Treatment
<i>Shared ILS & Collaborative Cataloguing</i>	
· Cooperative Cataloguing	B.1.2.6 Percentage of Rare Materials Accessible via Web Catalogues
	B.3.2.2 Median Time of Document Processing
	B.3.3.4 Employee Productivity in Media Processing
	B.3.3.6 Staff Costs per Title Catalogued
<i>Reference Services</i>	B.1.2.5 Speed of Reference Transactions
	B.2.4.3 Willingness to Return
	B.3.3.2 Correct Answer Fill Rate

<i>Staff Training</i>	B.4.2.2 Number of Attendance Hours at Formal Training Lessons per Staff Member
	B.4.2.3 Percentage of Staff Time Spent in Training
<i>Programs for Users</i>	B.2.2.4 User Attendances at Library Events per Capita
	B.2.2.5 Number of User Attendances at Training Lessons per Capita
<i>Needs of the Audience and General Impact of the Consortium</i>	
· Needs of the Audience	B.1.1.2. Percentage of Required Titles in the Collection
	B.2.1.1 Collection Turnover
	B.2.1.2 Loans per Capita
	B.2.1.3 Percentage of Stock not Used
· Needs of the Audience: E-resources	B.2.1.4. Number of Content Units Downloaded per Capita
· General Impact of the Consortium	B.2.2.2 Percentage of External Users
	B.2.2.3 Percentage of the Total Library Lending to External Users
	B.2.4.1 Percentage of the Target Population Reached
	B.2.4.2 User Satisfaction
* The coding (e.g. B.1.1.1. etc.) appearing before each p.i. is the unique number given to the indicator within the ISO11620-2014	

3.3 *Examples of ISO11620 p.i. in consortia environment*

We performed an analysis of the indicators under the prism of their suitability to assess consortia; the reduction of the indicators from the single library to the consortium environment entails specific changes in the calculation of each indicator. Due to the qualitative nature of the analysis, the presentation of these changes is indicative rather than exhaustive for all indicators. With this regard, we cite certain indicators that could be applied to measure performance in Cooperative Purchasing and Interlibrary Loan -the two most common services consortia offer-, in a Consortium's Funding and in displaying the General Impact of the Consortium.

3.3.1 *Example 1: an indicator for Cooperative Purchasing*

One of the most common services a consortium offers its members is a collaborative collection development program, usually for digital resources. One of four indicators that could be applied to measure the consortium's performance in cooperative purchasing, B.3.1.2 'Acquisition Cost per Collection Use' assesses "the library costs per collection use and therewith the cost-efficiency of library services" (International Organization for Standardization, 2014a). The method proposed to calculate the indicator is: "the total recurrent expenditure of the library in a full financial year divided by the total number of instances of collection use in the same period" (International Organization for Standardization, 2014a).

A library could apply this indicator to a collection provided by the consortium to assess the cost-efficiency. A second application is when a consortium calculates this indicator for a collection that has purchased. In this case, the consortium's expenditure and instances of collection use collectively for all library members should be counted.

3.3.2 *Example 2: indicators for Interlibrary Loan*

Resource Sharing and Interlibrary Loan for physical and electronic collections is as common a service as Cooperative Purchasing. The ISO11620 offers two relative performance indicators, one measuring the speed of interlibrary lending and another calculating the percentage of successful interlibrary loans.

A consortium or a library could assess the speed or the success rate of interlibrary loan for physical documents and of resource sharing for electronic document delivery separately, if they are two different services. The outcome could be used to compare performance between the member libraries or to monitor the service's efficiency with each passing year.

To calculate the B.1.2.3 'Speed of Interlibrary Lending', divide the total number of hours to complete a specified number of interlibrary loans or electronic document delivery transactions, using the log records of the ILL system, by the number of said loans/transactions. As the standard recommends, sampling, e.g. using a typical week, is possible.

To calculate the B.1.2.4 'Percentage of Successful Interlibrary Loans', divide the number of said loans/transactions by the total of all requests and multiply by 100. The same recommendation for sampling also applies in this instance.

3.3.3 Example 3: indicators for the Consortium's Funding

The p.i. B.4.3.1 'Percentage of Library Means Received by Special Grant or Income Generated' can be used to assess the consortium's success in obtaining additional financial resources, while p.i. B.4.3.2 'Percentage of Institutional Means Allocated to the Library' can be applied to measure the importance of the consortium (expressed in monetary units) and the support by the funding institution, in this case, the participating libraries.

To calculate the 'Percentage of Consortia Means Received by Special Grant or Income Generated', as the indicator could be renamed, the standard specifies that said means are divided by the overall means and multiplied by 100. The standard provides a definition for 'means received by special grants', for 'income generated', and for 'overall means' that can also be applied for consortia.

To calculate the 'Percentage of Institutional Means Allocated to the Consortium', as the indicator could be renamed, the consortium means are divided by the institutional means and multiplied by 100. The institutional means can refer to a single library's annual funding to assess this library's support to the consortium; the institutional means can also be calculated collectively, namely for all participating libraries to assess this consortium's support over a period of time.

3.3.4 Example 4: indicators for the General Impact of the Consortium and Needs of the Audience

To assess the general impact of the consortium, B.2.2.2 'Percentage of External Users' and B.2.2.3 'Percentage of the Total Library Lending to External Users' are ideal. In this case, external users can be considered libraries or agents -that are not members of the consortium- seeking a one-time access to the consortium's resources or services.

To assess if the consortium fulfills the needs of its audience, B.1.1.2 'Percentage of Required Titles in the Collection' is a great start. This indicator's objective is "to assess to what extent titles in demand by the users are owned or licensed by the library" and "to assess the fit of the collection to the requirements of the users" (International Organization for Standardization, 2014a). In applying the p.i., the required titles should be owned or licensed by the consortium or could be loaned between the participating libraries. The calculation method suggested in the standard is to compose a list of random requested titles and "record for each title in the sample whether the library owns or has licensed a copy of that title". In this case, we record ownership/license across each library's collections.

3.4 Comparing between KPI and ISO11620-2014 p.i.

Following the key areas listed by Appleton (2017, Ch. 9), various p.i. suggested in the standard could be used by a library to assess its performance in a strategic area. For example, ISO11620-2014 performance indicators could act as a measurement of:

- Customer satisfaction: B.1.1.1 'Required Titles Availability', B.1.1.2 'Percentage of Required Titles in the Collection', and certainly, B.2.4.2 'User Satisfaction'.
- Financial performance: B.3.1.1 'Cost per Collection Use', B.3.1.2 'Acquisition Cost per Collection Use', and B.3.1.3 'Cost per Download'.
- Internal processes: B.1.2.2 'Median Time of Document Retrieval from Closed Stacks' or B.1.2.3 'Speed of Interlibrary Lending'.
- Employee development and satisfaction: B.4.2.2 'Number of Attendance Hours at Formal Training Lessons per Staff Member' and B.4.2.3 'Percentage of Staff Time Spent in Training'.

Appleton (2017, Ch. 12) suggests indicative KPIs for academic and public libraries. We compared the Appleton's KPIs with the indicators of ISO11620 and the results are shown in Table 2. In the first and third column the indicators of each 'vocabulary' are mentioned respectively, while the second column provides (a) the semantic comparison between the scope the corresponding indicators and (b) the areas of measurement in which each ISO11620 p.i. belongs. Actually, only ten of the ISO11620 p.i. could be matched with the Appleton's KPIs.

Table 2: Comparison between KPI suggested in bibliography and ISO11620 p.i.

KPI suggested by Appleton (2017, Ch. 12)	Relationship/Areas of Measurement in ISO	ISO11620-2014 corresponding p.i.
Academic libraries		
% of PCs available at certain point throughout the day	Narrower than / Resource, Access, and Infrastructure	User Places per Capita (B.1.3.2)
% reading list items available in the library	Equal / Resource, Access, and Infrastructure	Required Titles Availability (B.1.1.1)
% reading list items available electronically	Narrower than / Resource, Access, and Infrastructure	Required Titles Availability (B.1.1.1)
Satisfaction rating in the National Student Survey	Equal / Use	User Satisfaction (B.2.4.2)
% increase of items placed in the institutional repository	Narrower than / Resource, Access, and Infrastructure	% of the Owner Institution's Publications in the Institutional Repository (B.1.1.5)
% increase in number of books digitized	Narrower than / Resource, Access, and Infrastructure	Number of Documents Digitized per 1.000 Documents in the Collection (B.1.1.4)
% staff who have attended internal training	Related to / Potentials and Development	Number of Attendance Hours at Formal Training Lessons per Staff Member (B.4.2.2)
Public Libraries		
Number/% increase of library users satisfied with access and opening hours	Related to / Resource, Access, and Infrastructure	Hours Open Compared to Demand (B.1.3.3)
Usage statistics of children's collections	Narrower than / Use	Collection Turnover (B.2.1.1)
Number/% increase in attendance at digital skills workshops	Narrower than / Use	Number of User Attendances at Training Lessons per Capita (B.2.2.5)

KPIs have narrower focus and measure the change rather than the status. For example, KPI 'Percentage of PCs available at a certain point throughout the day' is more specific in time and scope than the relevant p.i. B.1.3.2 'User Places per Capita'; KPI 'Percentage of increase in number of books digitized' focuses on measuring the change and in assessing the progress of a process rather than providing a number as p.i. B.1.1.4 'Number of Documents Digitized per 1.000 Documents in the Collection' offers. These differences underline the characteristics of a KPI: nonfinancial measures, measured frequently, used by the library's director, indicating corrective measures, influencing outcomes and results, and assigned to a

specific team. On the other hand, a performance indicator is “not critical to delivering the intended results, but help to align the activity of the service with the library's overall strategy” (Appleton, 2017, Ch. 10).

What is true for libraries is also applicable for consortia. Although ISO11620 indicators could be utilized to assess consortia services, they might not offer the ‘edge’ or the narrow focus to be used as KPIs.

4. Limitations

As far as limitations are concerned, our approach could be confirmed with real-world data; data should be collected with the same methodology (Poll, 2007) in order to be used for comparison purposes between consortia or libraries. A second limitation is that an indicator can contribute in measuring a certain aspect of the offered service; e.g. p.i. B.2.2.5 ‘*Number of User Attendances at Training Lessons per Capita*’ does not measure the quality of the training session or the change in the attendees’ skills/knowledge but contributes in measuring the performance in User programs.

The facilities of an individual library’s, in general, are not considered to be affected by its participation in a consortium. Moreover, libraries do not usually share spaces or create one for the use of the entire consortium, except for storage facilities. For these reasons, the following p.i. do not apply: B.1.3.1 ‘*User Area per Capita*’, B.1.3.2 ‘*User Places per Capita*’, B.1.3.3 ‘*Hours Open Compared to Demand*’, and B.2.3.1 ‘*User Places Occupancy Rate*’. Indicators that measure library visits should also not be used (B.2.2.1 ‘*Library Visits per Capita*’, B.3.4.2 ‘*Cost per Library Visit*’).

The limitations in the scope of each p.i., are transferred to the consortia that libraries participate. For example, B.1.1.4 ‘*Number of Documents Digitized per 1.000 Documents in the Collection*’ can be applied in libraries whose tasks include preserving documentary heritage, while B.2.1.1 ‘*Collection Turnover*’ is useful to libraries with a loan collection. Thus, a consortium will choose which p.i. to apply, according to the services offered, which in turn are dependent on the needs of the library members; their needs are -hopefully- aligned with their scope.

5. Conclusion

We found that ISO11620 p.i. can affirmatively measure the most common services consortia offer to their members: 46 out of 52 performance indicators could be applied for evaluating Collaborative Collection Development, Needs of the Audience and the General impact of the consortium, Consortium management, Collaborative cataloguing, Interlibrary Loan, Staff training, User programs, Digitization, Institutional Repositories, Reference Services, and Material Preservation. Several ISO11620 p.i. might be considered key, although this is heavily dependent on the purpose of the evaluation and the application profile: they could be adapted to narrow focus and calculated more frequently.

Applying an ISO standard has certain benefits one could reap: easy to apply, world-recognized, an established methodology to make comparisons, a well-known tool that came out of global research and consideration, to name a few. To our best knowledge, not many frameworks have been proposed for measuring or comparing the performance of library consortia. The proposed approach could contribute to the discussion on the performance measurement for consortia services and offer assistance in implementing the ISO11620 as a tool that libraries are already familiar with.

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